

21GRD03 PaRaMetriC

D8: Good practice guide for on-site performance assessment of PRC materials, with recommendations on how to monitor relevant ambient parameters, to achieve a target uncertainty below 10 % for the figures of merit

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Glossary

ADC	Analog to Digital Converter
CDT	Commercial Data Logger
EPS	Expanded Polystyrene (sintered)
FoM	Figure of Merit
IR	Infrared
NTC	Negative Temperature Coefficient
PRC	Passive Radiative Cooling
RCCS	Radiant-Capacitive Cooling System
STW	Sky Transparency Window

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1 Summary

Within the PaRaMetriC project, a dedicated work package addresses strategies for the evaluation of the on-site cooling performance of Passive Radiative Cooling (PRC) coatings, a critical aspect in the objective assessment of these materials. Indeed, experimental protocols and detailed methodologies are frequently underreported in the literature. Additionally, unlike classical laboratory measurements conducted under controlled conditions, PRC performance characterization requires outdoor measurements to ensure direct exposure to the sky. Such complex environments must be carefully monitored, as performance is strongly influenced by external parameters.

Currently, no standardized guidelines exist for PRC testing, and protocols and setups may vary across research groups. This document presents a set of experimental setups and complementary approaches developed during the PaRaMetriC project to illustrate the range of possible methodologies for testing these materials in different sizes, and under different thermal loads. For each setup, the employed methods and sensors are described in detail, including an uncertainty analysis of the relevant performance metrics. A comparative evaluation of the different designs is then provided to guide the selection of the most appropriate setup for accurate measurements. Finally, recommendations are offered for the precise monitoring of key environmental parameters.

2 Introduction

The field of research on Passive Radiative Cooling (PRC) is relatively recent but has experienced rapid growth since the breakthrough reported by Raman et al. [Ram14]. Because this technology requires direct sky access, accurately determining its key performance metrics is particularly challenging under continuously changing outdoor conditions. Indeed, the performance and equilibrium temperature of PRC materials depend on the environmental conditions in which the sample is situated, including ambient temperature, relative humidity, irradiance, wind speed, pollution and aerosol, altitude and tilting angle, among others [Gra81, Ber03, Che16, Zha19a, Zha19b, Ail21, Wan21, Tia23].

This highlights the critical importance of accurate monitoring of environmental parameters. Ideally, these parameters should be comprehensively measured, or at least indirectly quantified, within a standardized framework to contextualize experimental results. However, such full characterization is often lacking in the literature, and the use of varying measurement methods complicates the comparison of PRC performance across studies. For example, ambient temperature, which serves as the reference for determining the temperature drop (a key figure of merit presented within the next section), is highly sensitive to thermocouple placement and proper shielding from outdoor conditions which may bias the readout value [Lio24, Had25]. In some studies, the temperature of the air enclosure surrounding the sample, used when a windshield configuration is employed, is also reported as the ambient temperature [Bu23, Zho23, Sui24]. This value can differ significantly from the true ambient temperature, as it is influenced by overheating effects induced by the windshield, which in turn alters the measured temperature drop.

Moreover, the performance of the sample is influenced by parasitic non-radiative heat transfers, including convective and conductive losses. Conductive losses are strongly dependent on the design of the experimental setup, such as the type and thickness of insulating materials, which are rarely reported in the literature. No standardized PRC setup exists, and a wide variety of experimental configurations can be found in the literature.

Many factors can influence the behaviour of a PRC setup, particularly during daytime measurements. These include the use of reflective foils to redirect sunlight and prevent warming of the polystyrene base, the surrounding environment, the sample's height above the ground (e.g., on a pedestal system), its orientation [Bij24], and its tilt angle [Zha19a]. Inefficient design can lead to significant overheating, altering the local conditions around the sample.

Similarly, convective heat transfer has a strong impact on the sample temperature.

Consequently, the design of outdoor setups can have a significant impact on the quantification of PRC performance, making comparisons across different experiments challenging. Furthermore, uncertainty analyses of the FoM, which directly depend on the sensors employed and the characteristics of the experimental setup, are largely absent in the literature, despite being essential for reliable comparison of material performance. This is particularly critical because FoM values measured during daytime are relatively small, and large uncertainties may lead to misinterpretation of the results.

Within this context, this deliverable aims to present the various outdoor PRC testing setups developed by the project partners. For each setup, a detailed description of its design and the measurement protocols employed is provided. Prior to this, the main figures of merit for PRC materials are introduced.

3 Overview of the figures of merit and assessment methods

An appropriate procedure for determining the figures of merit (FoM) via on-site measurements has been developed based on the parameters identified in PaRaMetriC deliverable D1 [Tic23]. Two primary metrics are commonly used to represent the performance of a PRC material: the temperature drop relative to ambient conditions and the cooling power.

The first commonly assessed FoM is the temperature drop below ambient temperature, denoted as ΔT_{drop} (°C). It is defined as the difference between the ambient air temperature (T_a) and the surface temperature (T_s), corresponding to a null cooling power. Consequently, ΔT_{drop} is strongly dependent on the reference air

temperature, which may vary depending on the experimental setup and the configuration of any windshields used.

The second FoM is the maximum net cooling power, denoted as P_{cool} (W/m²). This represents the maximum cooling power that can be emitted by the PRC material when its surface temperature reaches that of the ambient air. Two measurement techniques are commonly employed to determine this FoM. The first technique involves direct measurement of the temperature difference between the inlet and outlet of a fluid in thermal contact with the sample [Gol17]. Knowing the fluid's mass flow rate and thermal properties, the cooling power can be calculated using the following relation:

$$P_{cool} = \dot{m}_{water} c_p \Delta T / A$$

Where \dot{m}_{water} represents the fluid mass flow rate, c_p is its heat capacity, ΔT is the temperature difference between the inlet and outlet of the device, and A is the area of the emitting surface used in the experiment. This method has the advantage of providing a conservative estimate of the cooling power, as any imperfect insulation in the experimental setup would lead to an underestimation of the FoM.

Alternatively, an indirect method employing an external heat pad can be used [Ram14]. In this approach, the sample is heated until it reaches ambient temperature using a feedback control system. It is commonly assumed that the electrical power supplied to the heater corresponds to the maximum cooling power of the material. However, this assumption may introduce a systematic bias, as not all the heat delivered by the external source is necessarily transferred to the sample, potentially resulting in an overestimation of the cooling power. Consequently, advanced heating systems incorporating graded heating approaches have been introduced in the literature [Ler19, Ler22].

These two complementary performance metrics are influenced by continuously changing ambient conditions. Ideally, to fully characterize PRC performance, both properties should be measured simultaneously under identical environmental conditions [Fan23, Wer25]. Achieving this requires two samples of the same material, one for measuring the temperature drop and the other for the cooling power, along with a more sophisticated data acquisition setup.

On-site testing prototypes developed during the project by the partners are illustrated in section 4.1.

4 Prototype realisations

4.1 CAE – air cooling

At CAE in Würzburg two setups have been developed and validated, an air cooling setup and a liquid cooling setup, which are described below. Würzburg is located in the northern part of Bavaria in Germany and is characterized by a moderate temperature climate (Köppen-Geiger climate classification Cfb).

4.1.1 Performance descriptor, measurement principle, and prototype design

For in-field testing an on-site setup has been developed, which determines the temperature drop or the cooling power, respectively. For testing PRC surfaces, the PRC materials have been applied onto aluminum sheets with the dimensions of 1000 mm x 500 mm x 1 mm. A thermal insulation is added to the coated aluminum sheets, i.e. the PRC surface is mounted on the top opening of one box as illustrated in Figure 1 together with a reference material, which is mounted on the top opening of a neighboring box. Both boxes are separated by a polyurethane (PU) foam with a thickness of 100 mm. All walls of the box consist of 100 mm thick PU-foam, except the openings on which the investigated surfaces are mounted. The investigated surfaces face towards the sky and the PU-foam walls are coated with a white adhesive film as shown in the pictures on the right in Figure 2. Using temperature sensors, the temperatures of the PRC material as well as the air temperature inside the boxes can be determined and subsequently the temperature drop below ambient temperature can be derived. For this purpose, environmental parameters are monitored as described in chapter 4.1.2. A fan in each of the two boxes provides a homogenous air temperature inside the boxes. For determining the cooling power instead of the temperature drop an electrical heater is placed in the box with the PRC material on top.

By measuring the heating power, which is needed to keep the air temperature T_2 in the PRC box at the same level as the air temperature T_1 in the reference box or as the ambient temperature T_{amb} , respectively.

Hence, the box provides two measurement modes: determination of the temperature drop of the PRC material in comparison to a reference material or determination of the cooling power of the PRC material in comparison to a reference material. For the first test mode the box is placed outdoor without electrical heating and the temperatures within both boxes are measured as well as the surface temperatures. For the second test mode the temperatures are measured, too. The electrical heater is switched on and is adjusted in such a way that the temperature in both boxes remains identical. The actual electrical power, which is needed to keep the temperatures identical, is determined as a function of time and is a measure for the cooling power. Alternatively, the temperature inside the PRC box can be adjusted to the ambient temperature in order to derive a more realistic value for the cooling power.

As the heat transfer (heat losses and heat gains) not only occurs through the PRC-material but also through the other walls of the box and the PRC performance strongly depends on the environmental conditions, measuring a reference material at the same time under identical conditions is advantageous. Furthermore, the environmental parameters need to be monitored.

Fig. 1: Schematic sketch of the air-cooling on-site setup at CAE for performing in-field measurements on PRC-materials. On the left the construction of one box with temperature sensors is depicted and on Fig. 1: Schematic sketch of the air-cooling on-site setup at CAE for performing in-field measurements on PRC-materials. On the left the construction of one box with temperature sensors is depicted and, on the right, the whole setup consisting of two boxes separated by a thermal insulation are shown. On the top of one box a reference material is placed whereas on the second box the PRC material is applied.

Fig. 2: Photo of the air-cooling on-site setup at CAE for performing in-field measurements on PRC-materials. On the left the construction of the setup with a white adhesive film on each side is shown and on the right the top of the setup with the reference material (here uncoated aluminium sheet) and the PRC material (here CaCO_3 -paint) is enlarged.

4.1.2 Monitoring of sample and environmental parameters

The equipment for measuring all relevant weather data (solar irradiation, relative humidity, amount of rain water, ambient air temperature, air pressure, wind speed and direction) is placed on the same platform where the test box is located (Figure 3). The equipment consists of several instruments. A pyranometer, which measures the irradiance on a plane surface which results from the direct solar radiation and from the diffuse radiation incident from the hemisphere above. The combination of a shadow ring with the pyranometer enables the separate measurement of the diffuse solar radiation. Further instruments are a rain gauge, a barometer, a humidity sensor, an anemometer and a temperature sensor with Stevenson shield (Figure 4).

Fig. 3: Experimental platform of CAE, where the on-site setups are located. The photo is taken from the CAE building, which is not visible on the picture.

Fig. 4: Weather station mounted at the experimental platform of CAE. On the right picture a part of the CAE-building is visible in the background.

4.1.3 Uncertainty budget estimation

The pyranometer covers a spectral range from 310 nm to 2800 nm with an uncertainty of ± 10 W/m². The uncertainty of the anemometer is ± 0.5 m/s in a measurement range up to 75 m/s, whereas the direction of the wind can be determined with a relative uncertainty of ± 2.5 %. The uncertainty of the barometer is ± 1 hPa in the measurement range from 900 hPa to 1050 hPa. The amount of rainwater can be determined with a relative

uncertainty of $\pm 5\%$. The relative humidity can be measured with an uncertainty of $\pm 3.5\%$. For the temperature measurements Pt1000-sensors have been used, which provide an uncertainty of $\pm 0.5\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

4.1.4 Experimental characterisation of the prototype

The prototype has been tested using different PRC materials. As an example, measurements of the temperature drop and the cooling power of a PRC-paint consisting of a polyurethane-acryl-paint with optimized CaCO_3 -pigments, which has been developed at CAE, have been determined. The surface temperature of the PRC-paint in comparison to a conventional white paint is given in Figure 5 together with the solar irradiation onto the surface. In contrast to the conventional white paint with a surface temperature around or slightly above ambient temperature, subambient cooling occurs for the PRC-paint during the whole day, despite the solar radiation. In Figure 6 the temperature drop of the PRC-paint has been measured in comparison to an aluminium surface. Again, subambient cooling is visible during the day, whereas the surface temperature of the aluminium surface lies significantly above ambient temperature. For validating the developed physical model for describing the heat transfer at the surfaces, the surface temperatures derived from the simulations are additionally plotted in the left graph of Figure 6. The resulting curves are in a good agreement.

Fig. 5: Determination of the temperature drop of the PRC-paint below ambient temperature measured during a sunny day in September in Würzburg (Germany) at CAE on the left. The monitored solar irradiation onto the surface is depicted on the right.

Fig. 6: Determination of temperature drop of the PRC-paint below ambient temperature measured during a sunny day in August in Würzburg (Germany) at CAE on the left. The dashed lines indicate the temperatures derived from simulations, which have been performed to validate the developed heat transfer models. The monitored solar irradiation onto the surface is depicted on the right together with the measured wind speed.

Finally, the cooling power of the PRC-paint has been determined in comparison to the aluminium surface as described above. The heating power, which is needed to keep the PRC-surface at the same temperature as the reference-surface, equals the cooling power of the PRC-paint. In Figure 7 the temperatures of the PRC-surface and the aluminium-surface are plotted together with the derived cooling power of the PRC-surface.

Fig. 7: Determination of cooling power of the PRC-paint measured during a sunny day in Würzburg (Germany) at CAE on the left. The monitored solar irradiation onto the surface is depicted on the right together with the measured wind speed.

For correlating the temperature drop and the cooling power of the PRC-paint with the optical and infrared-optical properties of the investigated surfaces, the spectral near-normal emissivity of the investigated surfaces are shown in Figure 8 together with the calculated values for the solar absorptance, the total hemispherical emissivity and the solar reflectance index (SRI).

Fig. 8: Left: spectral near-normal emissivity of the PRC-paint based on $CaCO_3$, the commercial white paint and the aluminum surface in the wavelength range from 0.25 μm to 35 μm . Right: solar absorptance, total hemispherical emissivity and solar reflectance index (SRI), which have been derived from the spectral near-normal emissivity according to the relevant standards.

4.2 CAE – liquid cooling

The second on-site setup at CAE operates by liquid cooling, i.e. heat exchange not only occurs by solar and thermal radiation and by convection due to air movement (natural and forced convection), but also by heat exchange with a liquid fluid, such as water. Therefore, a hydraulic water-flowing system has been applied for cooling the water which flows through the system.

4.2.1 Performance descriptor, measurement principle, and prototype design

A schematic drawing of the on-site setup with liquid cooling and the dimensions of 400 mm x 1000 mm is shown in Figure 9. Besides the PRC-temperature, the fluid temperature is measured at the inlet and the outlet of the hydraulic system together with the respective fluid flux. From these measurements the resulting cooling

power (or heating power) can be determined, which leads to a lower (or higher) temperature of a certain amount of water which flows through the setup. Photos of different stages of the preparation of the on-site setup are presented in Figure 10, Figure 11 and Figure 12.

Fig. 9: Schematic drawing of the on-site setup at CAE which operates by liquid cooling.

Fig. 10: View onto the rear side of the on-site setup prior to applying thermal insulation.

Fig. 11: View onto the front side of the on-site setup with thermal insulation on the back side.

Fig. 12: View onto the front side of the on-site setup where a white adhesive film is applied onto the thermal insulation.

4.2.2 Experimental characterization of the prototype

The on-site setup with liquid cooling has been tested in order to validate the homogeneity of the fluid flow through the prototype. For this purpose, a thermographic camera has been used for determining the surface temperature of the prototype. In Figure 13 and Figure 14 thermograms at two different temperature levels of the surface are depicted. In both cases the temperature distribution across the surface is homogeneous.

Fig. 13: Thermogram of the front side of the on-site setup with a given water flux through the setup.

Fig. 14: Thermogram of the front side of the on-site setup with a given water flux through the setup.

4.3 CP – Multi-sample temperature drop monitoring system

4.3.1 Performance descriptor, measurement principle and prototype design

The following experimental setup was designed to evaluate the outdoor performance of Passive Daytime Radiative Cooling (PDRC) materials by quantifying the temperature drop between the sample surface and the ambient air temperature, an approachable and common FoM in literature. Given that environmental parameters (irradiance, wind speed, humidity, etc.) significantly influence radiative cooling performance and vary dynamically over time, the setup enables the simultaneous testing of up to six samples under identical boundary conditions, allowing reliable performance comparisons.

The experimental setup is composed of two main subsystems: (i) the data acquisition and logging unit and (ii) the sample support and environmental instrumentation.

Data acquisition system

Temperature measurements are performed using a Keysight DAQ970A unit equipped with a DAQM901A multiplexer module, which allows for 22 channels (including 2 only for current measurement). The module enables automatic pairing of 4-wire RTD measurement channels, ensuring both source and sense connections for accurate readings. It also integrates a built-in thermocouple reference junction, minimizing potential errors arising from thermal gradients when measuring.

All temperature sensors (4-wire RTDs) used for sample and ambient temperature, are connected directly to the DAQ970A. The DAQ unit and the weather station logger are installed inside an outdoor-resistant cabinet, positioned adjacent to a north-facing wall to remain shaded during most of the day (Figure 15).

Sample support and environmental instrumentation

The sample holder, as seen in Figure 15, consists of a PVC pipe (30 cm diameter, 1.4 m height) supporting a wooden table-like structure on which the sample holders are mounted. To minimize parasitic heating effects, both the table-like support and the sample holders are wrapped in aluminized film with high solar reflectivity. The sample boxes are made of EPS (14 x 14 x 10 cm), with the PDRC sample mounted on the upper surface. Details regarding sensorisation of samples are provided in the following section. The configuration elevates the sample to 1.5 m above ground level, where vertical gradients of temperature are less pronounced.

In parallel, a second PVC pipe of the 15 cm lower supports a CMP6 pyranometer (Kipp & Zonen) used to measure incident solar irradiance. Additionally, a vertical steel support is installed behind the mentioned working bench to mount the weather station (7002571 PC Weather Station, Bresser) and a Th-Friedrichs type 2033 radiation shield housing the ambient temperature probe. All devices are positioned approximately the same height as the samples (1.5 m).

Fig. 15: Overview of the experimental setup. (A) Complete view of the sample support with a weather station and pyranometer. (B) Close-up of the weather station and the radiation shield. (C) Interior of the outdoor cabinet showing the DAQ units.

Test site conditions

The setup is located on a flat concrete floor, surrounded by open fields with low vegetation. Taller vegetation and walls (not more than 3-4 m high) are, at least, 10 m away from the test site, ensuring minimal shadowing and obstruction of direct sunlight. An overview of the sample perspective can be seen in Figure 16.

Fig. 16: Panoramic view of the surroundings from the perspective of the sample support, illustrating the viewing angle of the samples.

4.3.2 Monitoring of sample and environmental parameters

Temperature measurement

All temperature sensors used were Class A, 4-wire PT100 with 30 cm cabling (RSPPro). RTDs (Resistance Temperature Detectors) were selected due to their high stability, linear response and long-term accuracy, making them well-suited for extended outdoor monitoring tests. The 4-wire measurement configuration was mandatory in this setup, as the total cable length to the DAQ system was nearly 10 m. This method compensates for voltage drops in the connecting wires, thereby eliminating resistance errors and ensuring

measurement accuracy. The sample temperature was measured by attaching the PT100 sensor to the back center of each sample, using conductive silver glue (RSPPro) to ensure good thermal contact.

Moreover, the same temperature sensor type was used to monitor ambient temperature with a designated shield, as specified in one of the following paragraphs.

Irradiance Measurement

Irradiance was measured with a class B CMP6 pyranometer from Kipp & Zonen. The output voltage was logged directly by the DAQ970A and further converted to irradiance values (W/m²) using the calibration constant provided by the manufacturer setting the irradiance [W/m²] as proportional to 10⁵ x output [mV] / 10.27.

The pyranometer was positioned at the same height and in proximity of the samples to ensure that the irradiance values correspond precisely to the actual radiative conditions experienced by the samples. This minimizes discrepancies caused by shading, angular effects or local reflections.

Weather Station (other environmental parameters):

The ambient air temperature was monitored with the same 4-wire PT100 used for sample monitoring, housed in a Th-Friedrichs type 2033 radiation shield. This shield was then placed at the same height as the samples. The RTD was measured with the same equipment as the other temperature sensors (DAQ970A). This solution was preferred over the built-in Weather Station (WS) probe, as previous measurements and visible yellowing of the WS shield gave less accurate, higher temperature readings.

The Weather Station, (Bresser, 7002571 PC) was used to measure additional environmental parameters, including wind speed, relative humidity, atmospheric pressure and dew point. These variables are critical for contextualizing PRC material performance since they all significantly influence the net cooling power of radiative materials locally

4.3.3 Uncertainty budget estimation

Uncertainty in temperature (DAQ + sensors)

For the desired measurement range (0 – 100 °C), the Class A RTD probes specify an accuracy of ±(0.15 + 0.002|t|) °C. When measured by the DAQ970A, an additional measurement uncertainty of ±0.05 °C for this type of probe when measured within working operating range of 18-28 °C. Since the Datalogger is installed outdoors, even though shaded, summer ambient temperatures may reach up to 37 °C. Under such conditions, the datalogger added error per °C outside the specified range is 0.0006% reading + 0.0005% range / °C.

Moreover, the indoor characterization of such sensors resulted in differences of ± 0.17 °C relative to the mean value of the set.

Therefore, the combined uncertainty in the worst-case scenario (probe accuracy, experimental characterization and DAQ uncertainty and outside temperature range work contribution) is the following:

$$U(T) = 0.37 + 0.002|T| + \frac{d_{out}(T)}{0.385} (0.0056 + 0.00000231T)$$

Where d_{out} is the number of degrees outside of the 18 – 28 °C operating window.

Uncertainty in irradiance

The CMP6 Class B pyranometer has an uncertainty of 0.27 μV/(W/m²) = 2.64%.

Uncertainty in wind speed and relative humidity (weather station)

- Barometer: (700 ~ 1100hPa ± 5hPa) / (540 ~ 696hPa ± 8hPa) at 25 °C
- Relative humidity: 1 ~ 90% RH ± 2.5% RH at 25°C / 90 ~ 99% RH ± 3.5% RH at 25°C
- Wind speed: ±2.2 mph or ±10% (whichever is greater)

4.3.4 Experimental characterization of the prototype

Characterisation of the temperature sensors

The temperature sensors to be used in the measurements, either to monitor the sample or the ambient temperature, were characterized beforehand in a controlled indoor experiment. All probes were inserted into a 30 cm diameter copper cylinder, with thermal paste applied to guarantee a uniform thermal contact. The cylinder was insulated with a foam layer as seen in figure 17. Temperature readings were acquired with the same instrumentation employed in the outdoor setup, over a continuous 24-hour period with recordings each 10-second intervals (figure 17). Results show differences less than $\pm 0.17\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ relative to the mean value of the set.

Fig. 17: Indoor characterization of temperature sensors used in the setup and image of the sensors in the copper cylinder.

Optical characterization of setup materials

Prior to incorporating materials in the experimental setup, particularly those used for the sample holders, an optical characterization was conducted to evaluate their thermal behaviour. UV-Vis and FTIR spectra were obtained for the EPS, aluminized film and wood used (figure 18). The results confirm that covering exposed surfaces with aluminized film is essential, as it exhibits very high solar reflectance combined with low infrared absorption. EPS, while initially highly reflective in the UV-Vis range, degrades to a yellowish colour, thereby increasing solar absorbance. Its high infrared emissivity can be undesirable by enabling heat exchange with nearby objects. Wood shows a higher solar absorption and even higher FTIR emissivity than EPS, highlighting the importance of minimizing its exposure in the nearby areas of the sample.

Fig. 18: Optical characterization of sample support materials. (A) UV-VIS reflectance spectra and (B) FTIR absorbance spectra of EPS, aluminized film and MDF wood.

4.4 CSIC – full-scale demonstrator

4.4.1 Performance descriptor, measurement principle and prototype design

A full-scale experimental setup is used at the IETCC-CSIC to assess the performance of PRC materials in an operational building system. The setup is located in Arganda del Rey, Madrid, which has favourable climatic conditions for radiative cooling applications.

The full-scale test facility consists of two twin thermally insulated test cells, each measuring 15.2 m². The walls, ceiling, and floor are built with highly insulating modular panels (thermal conductivity $U = 0.0552 \text{ W/m}^2\cdot\text{K}$), minimizing external heat transfer. Each cell includes a south-facing high-performance window (Fig. 19).

Fig. 19: Full-scale test facility used for the IETcc-CSIC prototype.

A hydronic Radiant-Capacitive Cooling System (RCCS) is implemented in the experimental cell of the facility, consisting of three main components, as depicted in Fig 20 and Fig 21.

Fig. 20: Scheme of the Radiant-Capacitive Cooling System (RCCS) showing the three main components: Sky radiator (SR), Radiant Capacity Modules (RCM) and Thermal Energy Storage (TES).

Fig. 21: Diagram of components, sensors and water flow circuits of the Radiant-Capacitive Cooling System.

(a) Sky Radiators (SR) that comprise polypropylene panels typically used for heating swimming pool water. They have a surface of 2 m × 1.2 m each and a thickness of 5.5 mm thick (Fig. 22) and contain 4.3 mm internal diameter pipes through which water circulates. A 110 μm thick SPACECOOL Film-Silver film is adhered to the surface of the radiators to be exposed to the sky.

Fig. 22: Scheme of the Sky Radiators (SR).

(b) Indoor Radiant-Capacity Modules (RCMs), made of 1 mm thick steel sheet, baked white, with external dimensions of 0.9 m × 0.9 m × 0.07 m and an internal volume of approximately 52.5 l (Fig. 23). The volume of each RCM is occupied by a 3/8" (9.52 mm) diameter, 9.5 m long copper tubing coil acting as a heat exchanger, and by a volume of water equivalent to 51.8 l. Due to the water content, each RCM has a thermal capacity of 216.6 kJ/K.

Fig. 23. Radiant Capacity Modules (RCMs)

(c) Thermal Energy Storage (TES) system, includes two thermally insulated polyethylene water tanks with capacities of 1000 l and 50 l, respectively (Fig. 24). A hydropneumatic control system regulates water circulation through four different circuits, adjusting flow rates via solenoid valves.

Fig. 24: Thermal Energy Storage (TES) system with water tanks of 1000 l (TES-1) and 50 l (TES-2).

The system operates by dissipating heat via long-wave radiation to the sky, achieving water-cooling at night and, in specific conditions, also during the day using passive radiative cooling (PRC) materials. The cooled water then circulates through ceiling-mounted RCMs, providing radiant cooling for indoor spaces.

The cooling potential of the system can be assessed from measured water temperature data at the radiator inlet and outlet. The aim is to obtain the lowest possible temperature for a given water volume. The higher the water flow rate and the difference between the inlet temperature and the outlet temperature in the radiator (DT_w), the higher the cooling power. However, even with a temperature drop of the water passing through the radiator, that temperature may not necessarily be useful for cooling the indoor space. Water at the radiator outlet can only be used directly for indoor cooling if its temperature is lower than a set value, such as, for example, thermal comfort thresholds. Two types of cooling potentials can be assessed: a) the instantaneous or average cooling potential per unit area, as a function of the water flow rate and DT_w , and b) available cooling potential, taking into account a reference temperature, above which the cooled water would not be useful, so the system would stall.

The parameter used The radiative cooling potential per unit area of the sky radiators (CPSR) was calculated based on the water temperature difference between the radiator inlet and outlet and the water flow rate through it, as follows

$$CP_{SR} = \dot{m} \cdot c_p \cdot \Delta T / A \quad (4.1)$$

where CP_{SR} (W/m^2) is the instantaneous cooling power of the sky radiator per unit area, \dot{m} (kg/s) is the mass flow rate of water, c_p (J/kg K) is the specific heat of the water, ΔT (K) is the difference in water temperature between the inlet and outlet of the radiator, and A (m^2) is the surface area of the sky radiator.

4.4.2 Monitoring of sample and environmental parameters

The real-time data acquisition and control system is based on a Raspberry Pi 4B microprocessor, connected to a series of NTC acquisition modules, analogue signals, thermocouples, an electric meter, and AC actuators. These modules receive signals from a set of devices (14 PT100 probes, 8 thermocouples, two humidity meters, a weather station, a water flow meter, four 230 V AC solenoid valve actuators, and one 230 V AC water pump actuator). The variables measured are described in Table 3 and their location is included in Fig. 24.

Table 3. Description of the measured variables, sensor notation, probe type, and accuracy.

Measured variable	Notation	Probe type	Accuracy
Water temp. TES-1 at 0.1 m height	Tw1	PT100	$\pm(0.15 + 0.002 t)$ °C
Water temp. TES-1 at 0.8 m height	Tw2	PT100	"
Water temp. TES-2 at 0.3 m height	Tw3	PT100	"
Water inlet temperature in the SRs	Tw4	PT100	"
Water outlet temperature in the SRs	Tw5	PT100	"
Water inlet temperature in the RCMs	Tw6	PT100	"
Water outlet temperature in the RCMs	Tw9	PT100	"
Ambient temperature	Tamb	PT100	"
EC temperature at 1.2 m height	Tec1	PT100	"
CC temperature at 1.2 m height	Tcc	PT100	"
Reference temperature sample 1	Tr1	PT100	"
Reference temperature sample 2	Tr2	PT100	"
Reference temperature sample 3	Tr3	PT100	"
Reference temperature sample 4	Tr4	PT100	"
Water in RCM1	Tw7	Thermocouple T	+/- 0,5 °C o 4 %
Water in RCM7	Tw8	Thermocouple T	"
Surface temperature of RCM1	Ts1	Thermocouple T	"
Surface temperature of RCM7	Ts2	Thermocouple T	"
EC temperature at 2.2 m height	Tec2	Thermocouple T	"
EC temperature at 0.2 m height	Tec3	Thermocouple T	"
EC Globe temperature at 1.2 m height	Tecg	Thermocouple T	"
CC Globe temperature at 1.2 m height	Tccg	Thermocouple T	"

Water temperature values are measured at various locations throughout the system, as required for system performance analysis and to calculate performance indicators. For example, at the water inlet and outlet of the SRs, at the water inlet and outlet of the RCMs, at the TESs, and in the water inside of the RCMs. Water and air temperatures at key locations throughout the system are monitored using an RS PRO 4-wire PT100 RTD sensor, probe: Ø 6mm, length: 60mm, temperature range: -20°C → +200°C. Accuracy: Class A (IEC 60751). Tolerance: $\pm 0.15 + 0.002$ [°C]. The remaining water, air, and globe temperatures monitored were measured using T-type thermocouple probes. They have special accuracy, with special error limits: +/- 0.5°C or 4% of the temperature, whichever is greater. Temperature range: -200°C to 370°C. Fig. 25 shows the location of the temperature sensors installed inside the two prototype cells: ambient and globe temperature sensors at 1.2 m height in both the control and experimental cells and additional temperature sensors at 0.2 m and 2.2 m in the experimental one.

Fig. 25: Location of the temperature sensors inside the two cells of the prototype.

Regarding the water circuit, a Zenner ETWD-M flowmeter, DN15, with a nominal flow rate of 0 to 2.5 m³/h, and an EDC pulse module of 0.25 l/pulse, and an accuracy of $\pm 2\%$ in the nominal working range (permanent flow rate), are implemented. The water flow is adjusted using a pressure regulating valve located between the pressure tank outlet and the water meter, and two needle valves placed in the water return lines to TES-1 and TES-2.

An Optris CSmicro LT/LTH infrared thermometer is also used to monitor the "sky temperature" and analyse cloudiness or sky conditions. This very small infrared thermometer has a temperature range (scalable via software): $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $1030\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. System accuracy: $\pm 1.0\%$ or $\pm 1.0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Repeatability: $\pm 0.5\%$ or $\pm 0.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (3). Temperature coefficient: $\pm 0.05\text{ K/K}$ or $\pm 0.05\%/K$ (5).

4.4.3 Uncertainty budget estimation

Before installation in the final measurement locations, the sensors (PT100 probes and thermocouples) underwent a calibration process. This involved subjecting them to three temperature conditions—low, medium, and high—to analyse their measurement variability. The temperature differences among the PT100 probes were consistently less than $\pm 0.15\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ relative to the mean value of the set, with a standard deviation of $0.1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Similarly, the thermocouples were evaluated by examining the temperature differences between each thermocouple and the set average, as well as their standard deviations. In all cases, the temperature differences between individual thermocouples and the mean value remained below $\pm 0.13\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, with a standard deviation also of $0.1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

All measurements were recorded continuously at 5-minute intervals throughout the experimental periods, ensuring high temporal resolution and data consistency.

4.4.4 Experimental characterisation of the prototype

A set of experimental series has been carried out in the months of July to September 2024 and 2025, some of them in very hot climatic conditions, in order to answer the research questions. During these experimental series, some of the operating conditions of the system have been modified for this purpose, such as: the surface material of the radiators, the configuration of the panels forming the sky radiator, the number of RCM, the water flow rate, the amount of thermal storage and the operating time period of the system.

Some results related to three of the experimental series carried out in 2024 are presented below. The cooling potential at the radiator level (CP_{SR} defined in equation 4.1) and the characteristic temperatures of the experimental cell are used as indicators to allow comparisons of the system performance between the series.

In all the three series (B1, B2 and B3) the sky radiators have been coated with PRC material, TES-2 was used and the system operated in circuit 1 between 21:00h and 9:00h. Table 4.2 shows the operating conditions that Some results related to three of the experimental series carried out in 2024 are presented below. The cooling potential at the radiator level (CP_{SR} defined in equation 4.1) and the characteristic temperatures of the experimental cell are used as indicators to allow comparisons of the system performance between the series. In all the three series (B1, B2 and B3) the sky radiators have been coated with PRC material, TES-2 was used and the system operated in circuit 1 between 21:00h and 9:00h. Table 4.2 shows the operating conditions that were different in each of the series, i.e. the water flow rate (WFR) and the number of RCMs, and the values obtained for the cooling potential. CP_{SR} values between 43.4 W/m^2 and 58.3 W/m^2 can be observed, with maximum instantaneous values of up to 79.2 W/m^2 .

Table 4.2. Cooling potential obtained at three experimental series carried out in 2024 in different operating conditions of water flow rate (WFR) and number of RCMs.

Dates	Series	WFR	8-RCM	4-RCM	$CP_{SR} \text{ (W/m}^2\text{)}$	
					Avg	Max
21/08 27/08	to ES-B1	363	X		51.2	70.6
28/08 03/09	to ES-B2	170	X		43.4	78.3
04/09 07/09	to ES-B3	190		X	58.3	79.2

Table 4.3 shows the mean and maximum temperatures and the average daily swing of the monitored days in each experimental series. The following are presented as thermal performance indicators: the f value (decrement factor) = $T_{ec1}(\text{air temperature swing in the EC}) / T_{amb}$ (ambient air temperature swing); the DT_{avg} , which is the difference between the average ambient and air temperatures in the EC; the DT_{max} , which is the difference between the maximum ambient and air temperatures in the EC. The difference between the air temperature inside the CC and the EC (T_{cc-ec}) and the difference between the average ambient and EC temperatures (T_{amb-ec}) are also presented as characteristic indicators of system performance.

Table 4.3: Summary of characteristic temperatures and thermal performance indicators of the cooling system in experimental series B1, B2 and B3.

Series	Ambient			Control Cell			Experimental Cell			Performance Indicators			$T_{(cc-ec)}$		$T_{(amb-ec)}$	
	Avg	Max	Swing	Avg	Max	Swing	Avg	Max	Swing	"f"	DT_{avg}	DT_{max}	Avg	Avg		
	(°C)	(°C)	(K)	(°C)	(°C)	(K)	(°C)	(°C)	(K)		(K)	(K)	(K)	(K)		
B1	28.2	37.7	17.4	32.2	32.9	1.4	25.6	26.5	1.9	0.11	2.6	11.2	6.6	2.6		
B2	24.9	33.0	14.2	31.6	32.2	1.3	24.6	25.4	1.8	0.12	0.3	7.6	6.9	0.3		
B3	21.0	28.9	14.6	30.0	30.8	1.5	22.9	24.0	2.3	0.15	-1.8	4.9	7.2	-1.8		

Figure 26 shows the monitoring results during four continuous days of the experimental series B1, which represents the dynamics of the system and allows some observations about it. It is relevant to note that the reference temperature 3 (Tr_3 is the surface equilibrium temperature measured in the sample of the polypropylene radiator coated with PRC material) is always lower than the ambient temperature, even during the hours of highest irradiance ($I_g > 800 \text{ W/m}^2$). This confirms the particularity of the PRC material, which is capable of maintaining sub-ambient temperatures. This is understood by the depression of the reference temperature 3 (DTr_3 - Depression of the surface temperature Tr_3 with respect to ambient temperature) with respect to the ambient temperature (average values between $4.3 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $7.6 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, reaching up to $8.9 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$).

It should be noted how the water temperature in the RCM (T_{w8}) is reduced during the hours of operation of the system, thus giving it the possibility of absorbing heat during the day. The influence of the effective cooling potential of the RCMs to maintain the temperature in the experimental cell (T_{ec1}) within the comfort range is evident. The values are on average $3 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ lower than the ambient temperature and $6.6 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ lower than the control cell temperature (T_{cc}). This confirms the applicability and potential of the system to drastically reduce temperature peaks and maintain favorable conditions for thermal comfort.

In the experimental cell, where the RCMs are installed as ceiling panels, their low surface temperature relative to that of the interior wall, floor and ceiling surfaces allows for continuous heat dissipation 24 hours a day. The water in the RCMs, cooled during the operating hours, has allowed maintaining interior temperatures in the EC up to almost $7 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ lower than in the control cell.

Fig. 26: Monitored values of indoors (T_{ec1}), ambient (T_{amb}), reference (Tr_3), water temperatures in the RCMs (T_{w8}), and neutral temperature (T_n) with adaptive comfort ranges, in ES-B1, August 21th and 24th, 2024.

4.5 FIW – Multi-sample cooling power monitoring system

The cooling performance of PRDC materials can either be expressed as a temperature drop in [K] below ambient temperature that is caused by the heat-dissipation into space or by the net heat flux in [W/m^2], which is referred to as the possible “cooling power”. Both values depend on different factors. Such as thermal radiation from the emitter into space, absorbed solar irradiance, absorbed atmospheric downward longwave radiation, and non-radiative heat transfer between the surface and the ambient environment (e.g. humidity, convection). Overall measurement accuracy depends on the ability to correctly measure all these terms. Therefore, this study proposes a design based on a liquid-filled temperature control plate that allows the assessment of cooling power by measuring temperatures and heat flux. The research is about measuring the cooling capacity under real conditions with a high thermal load that can occur in various applications, e.g. in industrial heat exchangers, air conditioning systems, air-cooled condensers, and re-cooling units. These systems utilize higher temperatures to dissipate the heat energy into the environment. In most cases, heat transport is enhanced by convection using fans. Increasing the cooling power through radiation could contribute to lower energy consumption and higher system performance.

4.5.1 Performance descriptor, measurement principle, and prototype design

The prototype (Fig. 27) is designed to evaluate the cooling performance of four PRDC materials by measuring the temperature and heat flux generated by a temperature gradient between the samples and a liquid-filled temperature control plate. The temperature control plate can be operated at temperatures between $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $30\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ with a temperature variation of less than $\pm 0.2\text{ K}$. A thermally highly conductive levelling layer is placed between the temperature control plate and the carrier plate, where the PRDC samples are sealed. This layer is designed to compensate for the height variation caused by the sensor layer. It is highly flexible, ensuring all sensors are uniformly pressed down and perfectly thermally connected. The PRDC samples of $100 \times 100\text{ mm}$ consist of three different PRDC films (Sample 1, Sample 2 and Sample 3) whose properties, such as emissivity and reflectivity, have been evaluated during the PaRaMetriC project, and one commercially available tape (3M Long Lasting Tape), glued to a highly reflective aluminium substrate called “Vega 98®” (V98) provided by Almecco Group. The samples are attached to an aluminium carrier plate of 5 mm thickness. The carrier plate is enclosed with a sealing compound to ensure a watertight seal, which can also accommodate thermal expansion due to temperature variation. A reflective sheet paired with a semi-transparent protective screen of 1.5 mm thickness surrounds the samples on the top of the setup to avoid solar gains and thereby heating of the carrier plate. To minimize the heat transfer to the surroundings, the system is wrapped on all sides in an XPS insulation material (approximately $0.035\text{ W}/(\text{m}\cdot\text{K})$ and 100 mm thickness). Below the temperature control plate, the insulation of the system has been improved by adding a vacuum insulation panel (approximately $0.007\text{ W}/(\text{m}\cdot\text{K})$ and 40 mm thickness) beside the XPS board.

Fig. 27 Left: Explosion drawing of the measurement setup Right: Setup during measurement operation

The apparatus is optimized to measure the cooling power but can be used to measure the temperature drop as well with small changes in the setup. Parallel to the iterative development and implementation of the system, an entity-relationship diagram was created to visualize functions and uncover dependencies. Critical areas, for example, the sealing of the samples and the associated heat conduction from the edges were also analysed and then optimized using 2-dimensional simulation software for analysing the heat transfer. Simulation results showed no interference between the samples and no parasitic heat-flux (or -loss) disturbing the measurement. One example of the simulation results is shown in Fig. 27. The black curved lines are the isotherms. A sample temperature of 10 °C was used. The ambient temperature, as well as the temperature control plate temperature, were set to 20 °C. The parallel course of the isotherms below the sample shows that the centre of the sample in which the sensors are located is not affected by the connection to the other layers.

Fig. 28: Thermal simulation of the edge of the sample carrier (1) with the seal (2) and transition to the waterproof layer (3) and the protective screen (4). The levelling layer (5) is visible in the lower area of the heatmap.

4.5.2 Monitoring of sample and environmental parameters

For the monitoring of the samples, individually calibrated and rolled (thickness 0.2 mm) thermocouples (TC) type T (within ± 0.1 K) are used to measure the temperature below each sample and to monitor the temperature of the carrier plate. The heat flux sensors (accuracy within ± 3 %) of the size 18 mm x 18 mm x 0.5 mm are positioned below each sample.

The environmental parameters are monitored by a high-precision weather station located near the specimens. It is equipped with a multi-sensor system protected by a ventilated weather and radiation shield built at around 1.20 m above ground along with a pyranometer. Several environmental parameters, including particulate matter, atmospheric pressure (within ± 0.25 mbar) humidity (within ± 1.5 %), and air temperature (less than ± 0.1 K), are measured by the multi-sensor system. The pyranometer measures the incoming short-wave (from 0.3 to 2.8 μm with an uncertainty less than 5 %) and long-wave (from 4.5 to 42 μm with an uncertainty less than 10 %) Far Infrared (FIR) radiation and the surface-reflected short-wave and outgoing long-wave radiation. This instrument is also equipped with a temperature sensor (less than ± 0.3 K), which is used for the temperature compensation of the results. Finally, the weather station is equipped with an anemometer installed at 2.5 m above the ground and utilized to collect data on wind speed (within ± 0.1 m/s at 0 - 5 m/s and ± 2 % of value higher than 5 m/s) and direction (within $\pm 1^\circ$).

4.5.3 Uncertainty budget estimation

To measure the temperature, seven temperature points in the range from -20 °C to +40 °C were systematically selected for each thermocouple (type T); the measured thermoelectric voltages [V] were recorded together with the corresponding reference temperatures [K] (determined using an externally calibrated precision reference thermometer). The six factors for a fifth-degree polynomial were determined from the measurement pairs using least squares regression, whereby the coefficients a_i were determined by minimizing the sum of squares of the residuals.

$$T(V) = a_0 + a_1V + a_2V^2 + a_3V^3 + a_4V^4 + a_5V^5$$

The quality of the regression provides a polynomial-related measurement uncertainty of <0.01 K in the calibration range from -20 °C to +40 °C. Taking into account the uncertainties from the voltage measurement,

the temperature instability of the measuring environment and the residual calibration errors, the combined measurement uncertainty of the temperature measurement $\Delta T < \pm 0.1$ K results from linear error propagation.

The heat flux calculation is based on voltage outputs from the heat flux plates, which are converted into flux densities $[\text{W}/\text{m}^2]$ using the temperature-compensated conversion formula specified in the calibration protocol. The quality of the calibration factors used is specified as $\pm 3\%$ according to the manufacturer's specifications and represents the dominant systematic component of the heat flux uncertainty. The contribution to the flux deviation caused by the voltage measurement is $0.2253 \text{ W}/\text{m}^2$ in the present calibration case; with the maximum heat fluxes of approx. $300 \text{ W}/\text{m}^2$ recorded to date, this corresponds to an absolute measurement error of about $\pm 10 \text{ W}/\text{m}^2$. Therefore, the calibration uncertainty budget of $\pm 3\%$ is the most relevant factor for the total uncertainty of the heat flow measurement.

4.5.4 Experimental characterisation of the prototype

To measure the cooling performance on 8 March 2025, the temperature control plate in the unit was set to 18°C approx. 30 hours before the test. The samples are subjected to a constant thermal load, as it would be the case with heat exchangers in cooling systems, for example. The weather was very mild for March in Munich with air temperatures around the freezing point at night and a maximum temperature of approx. 17°C in the afternoon. There was plenty of sunshine and occasionally thin, high cloud fields. During the evening/night mostly clear. Weak winds ($0.1 - 2.4 \text{ m}/\text{s}$) were blowing from different directions. According to data from the German Meteorological Institute Deutscher Wetter Dienst (DWD), an average wind speed of $1.9\text{-}2.2 \text{ m}/\text{s}$ at a height of 10 m can be considered average for the location of Munich. The barometric pressure on this day was 951 hpa in the morning and dropped to 944 hpa during the course of the day.

Fig. 29. Measured wind speed and relative humidity of the air in the close surrounding of the samples

The diagram (Fig. 30) shows the time (exactly 24 hours) on the X-axis and the irradiance intensity in $[\text{W}/\text{m}^2]$ for long-wave (in red) and short-wave radiation (in yellow) on the left Y-axis. The blue dotted line shows the air temperature with the associated right Y-axis in $[\text{C}]$. The heat flux (cooling power) of the samples is plotted in $[\text{W}/\text{m}^2]$.

Fig. 30: Results of the cooling power measurement test on 08 March 2025 with temperature control plate set to 20 °C.

The short-wave radiation shows the typical circadian cycle for a cloudless spring day. The long-wave radiation is constant with a slight increase during the day. The samples show a strongly increased cooling power at night, which reaches -270 W/m^2 . With the increase in short-wave radiation (sunrise), the cooling capacity of the samples is reduced. At the time of maximum energy gain (12:30) with a short-wave irradiation of 650 W/m^2 plus the incoming long-wave radiation of 280 W/m^2 . The coatings achieve cooling capacities of -40 to -50 W/m^2 . As the solar radiation decreases, the cooling power increases again. On average, over 24 hours, including convective cooling, the reference sample achieves a cooling power of approx. -120 W/m^2 . The sample 3 and 2 are around -160 W/m^2 and sample 1 achieves approx. -170 W/m^2 . It is important to mention that these cooling capacities are not only the result of radiation. Convection is a key part of this cooling power. The reference sample is used as reference material due to the same layer arrangement as the other samples (highly reflective aluminium + thin polypropylene film). But instead of a PRC Material, a regular transparent adhesive Scotch Tape without any specific optimized emissivity properties is glued to the highly reflective aluminium substrate. It could be used as the baseline cooling capacity. By calculating the difference between the baseline and the other substrates, the difference should be assigned to the advanced radiative properties. The 24-hour average additional radiative cooling power for this day would be around -38 W/m^2 for sample 3 and -50 W/m^2 for sample 2. The sample 1 achieves approx. -53 W/m^2 .

4.6 INRIM – Open hardware platform for multi-sample, multi-FoM PRC assessment

The open-hardware system developed and tested in the Sesto Fiorentino branch of INRIM provides a versatile, open-source, and cost-effective method for accurately characterizing PRC performance. Furthermore, the propagation of measurement uncertainties allows both the determination of the FoM and the quantification of their associated uncertainties. Its design and working principles are described in the following subsections.

4.6.1 Performance descriptor, measurement principle and prototype design

As mentioned in the Overview of performance descriptors and assessment methods section, PRC material performance mainly depends on two parameters:

- maximum temperature drop ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) between the sample and the ambient temperature noted ΔT_{max}
- maximum cooling power (W/m^2) when the sample has the same temperature as the ambient noted P_{cool} .

To compare the cooling performance of different materials to a common baseline, it is desirable to test multiple PRC materials at the same time, thus ensuring that the results are obtained under identical environmental conditions. We present a fully open-source and open-hardware device offering up to 4+4 channels for the testing of both the maximum temperature drop and maximum cooling power at ambient temperature for multiple PRC materials. The resulting board is compact, lightweight and portable, it is easily assembled starting from low-cost off-the-shelf components. In addition to streamline the simultaneous comparison of multiple materials, the board allows monitoring of multiple parameters related to both external and internal ambient conditions, as well as the apparent sky temperature [Won23].

ΔT_{max} evaluation consists in sample and ambient temperature evaluation. Technical details of the measurement will be presented in the next section. Regarding the $P_{net\ max}$ evaluation, a widely adopted approach in the literature involves heating the sample from the rear using a thermal resistor until the sample temperature matches the ambient temperature [Man18, Fan23]. At the equilibrium, the electrical power supplied to the thermal resistor (via the Joule effect) directly corresponds to the cooling power P_{cool} of the sample under the assumption of 1-dimensional heat transfer through the sample surface. Maintaining this equilibrium requires the heat supplied to the sample to be continuously regulated through an electronic feedback loop, ensuring the sample remains at ambient temperature.

The measurement apparatus is driven by a device named FRESCO-board (Florence RadiativE passive Cooling Open-board) consisting of a main control unit (Arduino MEGA Rev3 or equivalent). The board can be programmed via a USB port and powered either through this port or a standard power supply (up to 12V, 1.2A). It can be connected to a wall power outlet or an external battery, such as a power bank, for off-grid operation. In the current implementation, the microcontroller drives two shields, named TDrop (for ΔT_{max}) and PCool (for $P_{net\ max}$), which can be stacked onto the main board. The first shield forms the core of the FRESCO system, handling temperature and environmental measurements, SD card data storage, and Wi-Fi communication (Figure 31). The FRESCO board with the TDrop and PCool modules can be assembled into a compact enclosure, which we realized using a Fused Deposition Modeling 3D printer (Anycubic i3 Mega), based on a 3D drawing which is also available on Zenodo [Wer25]. Figure 31C.1 shows a lateral view of the final device, while Figure 31C.2 displays the back view with the plug panel with labels for all connections. Figure 31C.3 provides a close-up of the internal wire connections within the enclosure.

Figure 31: Assembled PCB with electronic components and enclosure. (A) PCB for TDrop board; (B) PCB for PCool board; (C.1-3) The light gray boxes indicate the I/O pins used on the Arduino MEGA while the light green boxes indicate the variable name used for the measurements. Different views of the fully assembled FRESCO-board: (C.1) lateral, (C.2) back view of the plug panel and (C.3) inside with the electronic connection.

For our outdoor experiment, we used an aluminum rack measuring 90 cm in length, 40 cm in width, and 120 cm in height. The rack is divided into two shelves using wooden panels, with the lower section housing the FRESCO board. This section is protected laterally with 3 cm-thick expanded polystyrene (EPS) lateral walls to avoid direct sunlight illumination of the electronic board, while the other two sides are left semi-open to allow the free passage of ambient air, as shown in Figure 32A (left side). Figure 32A (right side) illustrates the arrangement of the samples on an EPS pedestal, showing details of the TDrop slot with the temperature sensor and of the PCool slot, which also includes a heating resistor. Schematic top-view, lateral view, and cross-sections corresponding to the colored planes cutting through the EPS pedestal help define the positioning of the samples for TDrop and PCool measurements (see top-view and zoom a). These views also clarify the placement of the negative temperature coefficient sensors (NTC) in direct contact with each sample (S#) and under each sample (U.S#) (see projections b-b and c-c), as well as the location of the resistive heater and its associated temperature sensor (see projection d-d). The sample holder is made of a 20 cm-high bulk EPS block, providing insulation from the ground and table shelf. The block has a total length of 80 cm, allowing it to accommodate four 6 x 6 cm slots in a 0.5 cm-thick EPS lid in a row avoiding sample shadowing. These slots securely hold equally sized samples, with a small gap underneath to house the temperature sensors and heating elements. The lateral walls of the block are wrapped in low-emissivity aluminum tape to minimize thermal radiation from the ground, while the top surface is entirely covered with a highly reflective solar diffuser film. The same film is also used as one of the tested emitters, which are applied on identical aluminum substrates. The surrounding temperatures of the sample environment with the lid and small air gap are also evaluated. The irradiance and sky temperature sensor are placed at a slightly higher height to avoid obstacles or shadowing during the day. Finally, a layer of polyethylene film is wrapped around the vertical posts of the rack to act as a lateral wind barrier (see Figure 32B), with the top left open to allow free air circulation around the samples. This setup prevents overheating of the surrounding environment while promoting natural airflow.

FRESCO is configured to measure samples with dimensions of 6 × 6 cm. However, assuming a conservative maximum cooling power of 170 W/m² per sample, the current system design limits the maximum sample size to approximately 8 × 8 cm. This limitation arises from the power constraints of the Arduino Mega power supply, which restricts the maximum power that can be dissipated by the resistive heating elements.

Figure 32: Experimental setup equipped with FRESKO-board for PRC outdoor measurements. (A) Schematic view of the apparatus with a detailed view of the EPS sample holder and the NTCs and heater position; (B) Photographs of the experimental apparatus highlighting the Light and IR sensors, the TDrop and the PCool slots with a detailed view of the NTCs connections and the heater resistor used in these configurations.

4.6.2 Monitoring of sample and environmental parameters

Monitoring the external test conditions is essential, as both the maximum temperature drop and the available cooling power depend on them. To this end, a range of sensors, listed below, have been integrated into the FRESKO datalogger:

- **Temperature Measurement:** Temperature data is captured using NTC thermistors (103JT, Semitec). The rationale for selecting this sensor type will be detailed below. The board provides five analog channels for temperature measurement.
- **Humidity Measurement:** DHT22 sensors (Aosong Electronics) are employed to monitor both air temperature and humidity at three different locations using three digital channels.
- **Light Measurement (Irradiance):** The BH1750 sensor (ROHM Semiconductors) measures irradiance in lux which is then converted in W/m^2 ($685 \text{ Lux} = 1 \text{ W/m}^2$).
- **Sky Temperature Measurement:** The MLX90614 sensor (Melexis) is an infrared thermometer designed for non-contact temperature measurements. Equipped with an IR-sensitive thermopile detector chip, this sensor provides qualitative readings of the apparent sky temperature, a parameter closely linked to instantaneous cooling performance. This sensor is sensitive to the wavelength between 5 and 14 μm which is a bit broader than the sky transparency window (STW).

Fig. 33: Pictures of the main electronic components used by the FRESCO system: (a) NTC; (b) DHT22; (c) MLX90614; (d) BH1750; (e) HS25E3 100R F M145.

The FRESCO device employs NTCs thermistors to measure temperature. These sensors exhibit a non-linear resistance/temperature relationship, which can be described by the Steinhart–Hart equation (Eq. 1). The four coefficients a, b, c and d are determined by fitting the manufacturer's resistance/temperature characteristic of the NTC.

$$T_{NTC} = a + b \ln \frac{R_T}{R_0} + c \ln \left(\frac{R_T}{R_0} \right)^2 + d \ln \left(\frac{R_T}{R_0} \right)^3 \quad (4.2)$$

where R_T is the thermistor resistance and R_0 is the resistance at the reference temperature (most of the time $T_0 = 25^\circ\text{C}$). For simplicity, the Steinhart–Hart equation is often approximated by a single-parameter expression, commonly referred to as the Beta law, as described below

$$T_{NTC} = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{T_0} + \frac{1}{\beta_{NTC}} \ln(R_T/R_0)} \quad (4.3)$$

Either Eq. 4.2 or Eq. 4.3 can be implemented on the FRESCO board, depending on the user's accuracy and uncertainty requirements. NTC thermistors were chosen over the more commonly used PT100 sensors due to their ease of integration within the FRESCO board and their small contact surface, which facilitates localized measurements compared to the bulkier PT100 sensors.

The contact between the NTC and the sample is ensured using a thermal paste (thermal conductivity > 3.5 W/m K) and a layer of adhesive Kapton (3M Polyimide Film Electrical Tape 92) on its back. The heating resistor is directly attached to each sample using a bi-adhesive thermal tape (3M Thermally Conductive Interface Tape 8926). Figure 32B shows the used NTCs and resistive heaters and their position with respect to the EPS pedestal.

Prior to setting up the experiment, NTC sensors should be characterized in a controlled environment to verify their compliance with the manufacturer's technical specifications. When compared among themselves or to a reference sensor, small systematic deviations are typically observed, with some sensors displaying slightly higher and others slightly lower readings. To adopt a conservative approach and minimize the risk of overestimating the cooling performance of a PDRC coating, we recommend using slightly "hot" sensors for sample measurements and slightly "cold" sensors for ambient temperature monitoring, in order to avoid the risk of overestimating the sub-ambient cooling effect.

When mounting the NTC sensors and electric heaters, care should be taken to ensure good thermal contact with the sample substrates. This can be done by attaching the sensors to the metal with Kapton tape to further shield the sensors from ambient temperature fluctuations. Thermal paste should be applied sparingly or be

replaced with thin thermal double-tape, to ensure that the adhesion between the substrate and the Kapton tape is not weakened.

Another key element for any PRC testing experiment is the accurate measurement of ambient temperature. To this purpose, the ambient temperature sensor should be placed at an appropriate distance from the ground (at least 1.25 m following recommendations from the World Meteorological Organization) and properly shielded from solar radiation [Bu23]. Figure 32B shows a picture of our setup equipped with a commercial radiation shield (SKU 7714, Davis, USA) fixed at a height of 1.25 m. Most importantly, a good ambient temperature measurement requires a good radiation shield configuration which protects the sensor from external heat sources such as solar radiation and ground reflections while allowing free airflow. Modern designs use plastic radiation shields, which are lighter, more compact, and easier to manage. Various Stevenson shields are available on the market, but they can yield significantly different ambient temperature readings depending on factors like plastic quality, thickness, UV blockers, shapes and emissivity spectrum. Comparison between high quality and low quality Stevenson shield for ambient temperature measurement is available at this reference [Lio24a].

Lastly, describing the Pcool board architecture, the main components are:

- Heating Resistor: the HS25E3 100R F M145 heating resistor has been selected for this application due to the small sample size (5 × 5 cm). This resistor was preferred over heating pad resistors because of its cost-effectiveness and ability to provide a uniform temperature across the sample surface.
- Feed-back loop system: a classical PID (Proportional-Integral-Derivative) control system is employed in conjunction with an IRLR014NTRPBF MOSFET to regulate the power supplied to the heating element via pulse-width modulation (PWM). This setup ensures precise control of the heating process.
- Electrical power measurement: current through the heating element is measured using a shunt resistor, coupled with the AD820 differential amplification system. This system incorporates a third-order filter to enhance the accuracy and precision of current measurements.

Once the heating elements are mounted on the PCool channels, their voltage drop should be measured and stored in the relative PSUPPLY_VOLTAGE variable in the Arduino firmware. With a 12 V external power supply, typically around 10.8 V are available at the heating resistors accounting for the voltage drops introduced by the MOSFET and internal diodes. Once this value is set, PID parameters can be tuned during a laboratory test session by setting a constant target temperature above ambient conditions and tracking the system time response. To this purpose, FRESCO-board allows setting the PID target temperature to track the reading of another sensor (by default, the sensor tracking ambient temperature), or to a constant user-defined temperature.

For our system, we determined values of 225, 0.75 and 10 for the proportional, integral and derivative parameters, respectively. These parameters are specific to the experimental configuration and may vary depending on the sample size and substrate material used. For tuning the PID parameters, the closed-loop Takahashi method is recommended [Tak19].

4.6.3 Uncertainty budget estimation

The uncertainty propagation analysis of the FRESCO device was conducted to quantify uncertainties in both maximum temperature drop and cooling power. The NTC sensor selected for this study is the 103JT-025 with a nominal resistance of $10\text{ k}\Omega \pm 1\%$ at 25°C and $\beta_{NTC} = 3435\text{ k}\Omega \pm 1\%$. Final results are presented in Figure 34, while intermediate results, methods for total uncertainty evaluation in function of the used sensor, with the full calculation available in the online repository of the associated publication [Wer25]. Uncertainty was computed using the four-coefficient Steinhart–Hart equation in combination with Monte Carlo simulations for coefficient uncertainty estimation. All calculations followed the *Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement (GUM)* [JCGM08].

Fig. 34: (a) Relative Extended ΔT uncertainty map in function of ΔT with the green zone representing when the value is beneath 10% of the total value (b) Relative Extended P_{cool} uncertainty map in function of ΔT .

4.6.4 Experimental characterization of the prototype

Comparison against a commercial data logger

The performance of the FRESCO board has been evaluated against a commercial data logger (CDT) equipped with a PT100 temperature sensor. This serves the twofold purpose of verifying the long-term stability of NTC sensors against the PT100, and to check that all used sensors are within the tolerances provided by the manufacturer. The test was conducted over a 48-hour period, and all sensors were attached to the back of a metallic plate, following the same experimental protocol to ensure consistency. The CDT was equipped with a single PT100 sensor, while the FRESCO device used five NTC thermistors. As shown in Figure 35A, the temperature readings from both systems exhibited similar trends, with an absolute temperature difference with respect to the PT100 limited to a maximum of 0.6 °C at 20 °C as expected per the specification. The black dashed line represents the PT100, while the colored solid lines represent the temperature difference of the five NTCs. Finally, the solid cyan curve shows the temperature measured using a digital temperature sensor (DHT22) close to the measurement region (not in contact with the aluminum plate). The presence of possible temperature drifts between the NTCs and the PT100 was evaluated by taking the derivative of the difference between each sensor and the PT100. This operation shows a flat trend, indicating the absence of drifts over timescales of hours or days.

Fig. 35: Comparison between Fresco and a commercial data logger. (A) Temperatures of both devices during the acquisition. (B) Derivative of the temperature difference between the two devices to verify the absence of NTC drifts with respect to the CDT.

Dynamic range and dependence of the IR sky temperature sensor on measurements conditions

Sky equivalent temperature, if not the most important parameter for PRC, plays a direct role on sample performance and can be correlated to it. Therefore, it needs to be quantified at least qualitatively while performing outdoor experiments. For this purpose, we decided to use a contact-less infrared temperature sensor in order to monitor this variable during outdoor experiments: MLX90614. This sensor is sensitive to the wavelength between 5 and 14 μm which is a bit broader than the STW. MLX90640 IR temperature sensors to evaluate its suitability for sky temperature measurements. In the first test, we checked whether the sensor offers a compatible measurement range, capable of reading also very cold temperatures. To this purpose, we oriented it towards the inside of a laboratory freezer set at a temperature of $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Figure 36A). The experiment shows that the sensor is able to reach such low temperatures, going from room temperature ($20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) to the object temperature ($-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) and back to room temperature after the freezer door is closed, in a matter of seconds. This test demonstrates that the sensor works according to its specifications, and that its implementation allows reading its response over the full range. Two subsequent tests were performed in rapid succession by allowing the sensor to measure the sky temperature at our typical measurement location ($43^{\circ} 49' 7.9'' \text{ N}$, $11^{\circ} 11' 36.8'' \text{ E}$) at an altitude of 50 m (Figure 36B), and on top of a nearby hill ($43^{\circ} 50' 33.3'' \text{ N}$, $11^{\circ} 14' 46.8'' \text{ E}$) at an altitude of 590 m (Figure 36C). The sky temperature in these two cases experiences a significant drop from -17°C to -23°C , showing that the MLX90640 is sensitive to the higher atmospheric transparency expected in the second location, both due to its higher altitude and lower aerosol and pollution.

Figure 36: Minimum temperature range and altitude dependence of MLX readings (A) Temperature measured pointing the MLX towards the inside of a freezer at -80°C . (B) Sky temperature measured using the MLX in an open field at an altitude of 50 m. (C) Sky temperature measured shortly after using the MLX at an altitude of 590 m (Monte Morello, Florence).

Monitoring of temperature beneath the sample slot

Temperature sensors positioned beneath the samples indicate that the small enclosed air pocket below each sample remains at a temperature slightly above that of the samples. This suggests that in general, the presence of an air pocket beneath the samples, albeit small, can represent a hindrance to the full manifestation of the radiative cooling effect [Wer25, Lio24b].

4.7 INRIM – Medium-size experimental setup

4.7.1 Performance descriptor, measurement principle and prototype design

The INRiM medium-size apparatus measures heat transfer from a PRC material to ambient using a calorimetric technique. A temperature-controlled fluid circulates beneath a PRC-coated surface. By monitoring the fluid's inlet and outlet temperatures at a constant flow rate, the net heat absorbed or released by the surface is calculated. During the test, both the inlet/outlet water temperatures and water flow rate are measured simultaneously along with the various environmental conditions (ambient temperature and humidity, solar irradiance, wind speed, etc.).

The experimental setup (Figure 37) consists of a water vessel made of polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) sealed by an aluminium plate (0.8 mm thick) where the PRC material is applied (50 cm x 50 cm).

The water path behind the PRC panel has been designed to make its flow as uniform as possible across the entire back surface of the panel. To do this, a multiple input/output dichotomous distribution of the fluid was adopted.

The enclosure box is made of high-density expanded polystyrene foam (EPS) with a wall thickness of 10 cm. A mylar sheet was applied on the top and lateral sides of the box (just excluding the large bevel facing the sample's surface) to reduce the heating of the box.

Several temperature sensors (NTC) are placed in the water flow to monitor the temperature at different locations behind the PRC panel. While a multi-junction type-T differential thermocouple is used to directly measure the temperature difference between inlet and outlet. Finally, a flow meter is employed for water flow measurement.

Fig. 37: Medium-size experimental setup developed at INRiM. (a) working principle; (b) technical drawing; (c) thermal sensor location; (d) a photo of the setup during in-field tests

4.7.2 Monitoring of sample and environmental parameters

Temperature and flow measurement

An original aspect of the setup is the use of a differential multi-junction Type-T thermocouple (thermopile). This configuration, with thermocouple junctions every two channels (total 32), amplifies the voltage response by approximately 16 times compared to a single-junction thermocouple, providing exceptional sensitivity.

Five Negative Temperature Coefficient (NTC) thermistors are also embedded in the fluid path (inlet, outlet, center, and panel edges) for comprehensive spatial temperature mapping, revealing asymmetries and validating thermal equilibrium.

The thermopile was characterized to determine its sensitivity ($657.7 \mu\text{V}/^\circ\text{C}$ near ambient temperature, with 12.4 mK uncertainty) and correct for parasitic electromotive forces. NTC sensors were calibrated against a Standard Platinum Resistance Thermometer (SPRT) from 10°C to 40°C with an uncertainty of 0.05°C , ensuring traceability to national standards (ITS-90). Figure 40C schematically shows sensor locations.

A thermostatic circulation bath controls the water temperature feeding the panel. Water flow rate is continuously measured by a KROHNE AF-E 400 flow meter, calibrated against Italian national standards.

All temperature sensors and the flow meter's analog output connect to a 6.5-digit multimeter via a scanner for automatic data acquisition.

Measurement configurations and auxiliary mode

The setup offers two measurement configurations:

- **Static:** Still water under the sample allows measuring the temperature drop between the PRC and ambient using embedded thermometers.
- **Dynamic:** Flowing water allows evaluating the PRC material's cooling power using the thermopile to measure the inlet-outlet temperature difference.

An auxiliary mode for estimating radiative power loss is integrated, using a resistive heating wire in the channels. By supplying current to maintain the aluminum plate at ambient temperature, the required electrical power equals the radiative power loss, offering a secondary, precise method for quantification.

Environmental monitoring

Environmental parameters like ambient temperature, humidity, wind speed, and solar irradiance are continuously monitored by a MaxiMet GMX501 weather station near the device. An Optris CSmicro IR temperature sensor ($8\text{-}13 \mu\text{m}$) aimed at the zenith monitors apparent sky temperature down to -50°C . Data from both are acquired and stored on a PC using proprietary software.

4.7.3 Uncertainty budget estimation

To validate design and optimize operation, we analysed the combined uncertainty of the measurement system, focusing on water flow and temperature difference. Other sources, like water density variation, were deemed negligible.

Flow meter uncertainty analysis

The flow meter's inherent uncertainty, crucial for energy calculations, is based on calibration data (expanded uncertainty $U_{k=2}$ across different nominal flow rates (Q_{NOM})). For unlisted flow rates, a linear fitting method determines uncertainty. Figure 38 shows calibration results, with decreasing relative uncertainty at higher flow rates.

Fig. 38: Results and expanded calibration uncertainty $U_{(k=2)}$ of the flow meter used in the setup. Q is the volumetric flow rate measured by reference standard (Q_{REF}) and sensor in calibration (Q) referred to nominal value (Q_{NOM}).

Thermistor uncertainty analysis

Thermistors have an assumed expanded calibration uncertainty $U_{k=2}$ of 0.05 °C, yielding a standard uncertainty (u) of 0.025 °C. For differential temperature measurements, uncertainties are propagated using the root sum of squares method, resulting in a combined absolute expanded uncertainty $U_{k=2}$ of 0.071 °C for temperature difference.

The relative uncertainty for NTCs, derived from this absolute uncertainty, depends on the measured temperature difference (ΔT). This relative uncertainty, combined with the flow meter's relative uncertainty, gives the system's overall relative uncertainty. A critical finding is that a small ΔT (e.g., less than 0.7 °C) leads to a disproportionately large relative uncertainty, preventing the system from meeting the target uncertainty of below 10 %. The thermistors' calibration uncertainty is the primary driver of overall measurement uncertainty, making them unsuitable for small temperature differences.

Multi-junction thermocouple uncertainty analysis

As an alternative, a Type-T differential multi-thermocouple with 16 junctions was analysed. This design amplifies the signal and reduces relative uncertainty. With a single TC-T sensitivity of 41.106 $\mu V/^\circ C$, the 16-junction TC's overall sensitivity is 657.696 $\mu V/^\circ C$. The uncertainty of this sensitivity, derived from temperature variations (25 °C to 35 °C), is 0.852 $\mu V/^\circ C$, which converts to a standard uncertainty of 0.2459 μV . Due to correlation between junctions, the combined uncertainty is:

$$u_{16} = 16 * u_1 = 3.935 \mu V$$

Including the 6½-digit multimeter's uncertainty ($u_{DMM} = 1.0 \mu V$), the combined standard measurement uncertainty is

$$u_c = \sqrt{u_{16}^2 + u_{DMM}^2} = 4.06 \mu V$$

This results in a temperature uncertainty of 0.0062 °C, significantly lower than thermistors, directly due to the multi-junction design. The thermopile measures ΔT with an expanded uncertainty of 12.4 mK.

Similar to thermistors, the relative uncertainty for the multi-thermocouple is calculated as a function of ΔT and then combined with the flow meter's relative uncertainty. Figure 39 shows a 3-D graph of the total expanded uncertainty as a function of measured ΔT and nominal flow rates. All values are below the 10 % target uncertainty, except for measured temperature differences below 0.1 °C. This demonstrates the multi-junction thermocouple's effectiveness in meeting accuracy targets across nearly its entire operational range, a significant improvement over thermistor setups.

Fig. 39: Total expanded uncertainty as a function of measured temperature difference and nominal flow rates.

4.8 TUBITAK – Outdoor variable inclination setup

4.8.1 Performance descriptor, measurement principle and prototype design

The setup shown in Figure 40, was established to measure the temperature reducing performance of Passive Daytime Radiative Cooling (PDRC) materials (Sample 1, Sample 2 and Sample3) in an outdoor environment. The measurement system consists of a meteorological station having irradiance, ambient temperature, wind speed and direction sensors, a thermally isolated sample test box, the data acquisition and logging units.

The whole system was installed on the roof of a two-floor building, away from any obstacles that could affect wind speed and irradiance. Locations of the sensors of meteorological stations were determined according to IEC 61215-2 standards that have been used for the performance measurements in photovoltaic applications. The supporting system as shown in Figure 40, used to mount the sensors and a thermally isolated sample test box, was designed such a way that (above 0.6 m local horizontal plane or ground level), it minimizes heat conduction and the interference of heat between sensors and the thermally isolated sample test box. The pyranometer was mounted to the supporting system almost within 0,3 m, in the plane of the thermally isolated sample test box, the wind sensor was installed approximately 0,7 m above the top of thermally isolated sample test box in a position where it will not shade the PDRC materials.

The thermally isolated sample test box constructed for the temperature-reducing performance measurements of PDRC materials is shown in Figure 41, has two sections each with 40 cm x 40cm x 25cm dimensions. To achieve high insulation, this thermally isolated sample test box was made from a foam, covered with glass wool and wood. One of the sections in this thermally isolated sample test box is used for the temperature measurements of substrate and another one is used for the temperature measurements of substrate + PDRC materials. The substrate used for these tests is aluminium with 1 mm thickness. In each section of the thermally isolated sample test box two Pt 100 temperature sensors are located. One of these sensors was attached just under the samples, another one was hung inside the empty space as shown on the lower right side of Figure 40.

In this measurement system two data acquisition and recording units were used. One was used to collect and record data from the irradiance, ambient temperature, and wind speed sensors, and the other was used to collect and record data from the temperature sensors inside the thermally isolated sample test box.

Fig. 40. Outdoor temperature reducing measurement facility

Fig. 41: Thermally isolated sample test box, replacement of PDRC materials and characterization of temperature sensors

4.8.2 Monitoring of sample and environmental parameters

In this work the temperature-reducing capacity of three different Passive Daytime Radiative Cooling materials (Sample 1, Sample 2 and Sample 3) was measured.

Before the measurements, the calibrations of all sensors used in this system were carried out at the national metrology institute of Türkiye, which is called TUBITAK UME. At the measurement stage, initially insulation capabilities of the sections in the thermally isolated sample test box, then the offset differences in the sensors used in these measurements were investigated. After that, each time a pair of samples shown in Figure 41 respectively placed to the sample holders of thermally isolated sample test boxes and the measurements were performed. The data generated both from the meteorological sensors (irradiance, ambient temperature and wind speed sensors) and the temperature sensors from the thermally isolated sample test box were measured by the related data acquisition and recording units. The measurements with the measurement system set to 0° inclination angle were carried out between June and July, and the measurements with the measurement system set to 37.5° inclination angle were carried out between August and September. The measurement results obtained for all PDRC materials are given in Figure 42-Figure 44, respectively.

Fig. 42. Temperature reducing capacity of Sample 1 at 0° (left) and 37.5° (right) inclination

Figure 43. Temperature reducing capacity of Sample 2 at 0° (left) and 37.5° (right) inclination

Figure 44. Temperature reducing capacity of Sample 3 at 0° (left) and 37.5° (right) inclination

4.8.3 Uncertainty budget estimation

According to the IEC 61853-2 standard the temperature of a device over a range of environmental conditions can be evaluated using the relation

$$T_m = T_{amb} + \frac{G}{u_0 + u_1 \cdot v} \tag{4.4}$$

where T_m is the temperature of the measured device, T_{amb} is the ambient temperature, G is the total solar irradiance incident on the active surface of the device, v is the wind speed, u_0 and u_1 are the coefficients, respectively described the influence of the irradiance and the wind impact on the temperature.

Using Eq. (4.4) to calculate the temperatures of PRC materials exposed to irradiance, ambient temperature, and wind speed, it is necessary to first calculate the u_0 and u_1 coefficients after measurements. To do this, first plot the $G/(T_m - T_{amb})$ versus wind speed and evaluate u_0 and u_1 coefficients from the intersection of the graph with the axis and the slope. Then using these coefficients, the temperatures of PRC materials can be calculated. Since Eq. (4.4) is used in the calculation of the temperatures of PRC materials, the following equation derived from this equation can be used to calculate the uncertainties in the temperatures of these materials

$$T_m(\delta_{ac}T_m + \delta_{res}T_m + \delta_{cert}T_m) = T_{amb}(T_{amb} + \delta_{ac}T_{amb} + \delta_{res}T_{amb} + \delta_{cert}T_{amb}) + \frac{G(G + \delta_{ac}G + \delta_{res}G + \delta_{cert}G)}{u_0 + u_1v(\delta_{ac}v + \delta_{res}v + \delta_{cert}v)}$$

The parameters in this equation are given in the following list. Using this equation the uncertainty calculated for the three tested passive cooling samples are between 8 % and 10 %.

T_m	Measured temperature by Pt100
$\delta_{ac}T_m$	Pt100 accuracy
$\delta_{res}T_m$	PT100 resolution
$\delta_{cert}T_m$	PT100 calibration certificate
T_{amb}	Temperature determined by ambient sensor
$\delta_{ac}T_{amb}$	Ambient sensor accuracy
$\delta_{res}T_{amb}$	Ambient sensor resolution
$\delta_{cert}T_{amb}$	Ambient sensor calibration certificate
G	Measurement by irradiance sensor
$\delta_{ac}G$	Irradiance sensor accuracy
$\delta_{res}G$	Irradiance sensor resolution
$\delta_{cert}G$	Irradiance sensor calibration certificate
u_0	Intersection point determined from $G/T_m + T_{amb}$
u_1	Slope determined from $G/T_m + T_{amb}$
v	Measurement of wind speed sensor
$\delta_{ac}v$	Wind speed sensor accuracy
$\delta_{res}v$	Wind speed sensor resolution
$\delta_{cert}v$	Wind speed sensor calibration certificate

5 Best practices for monitoring ambient parameters

Weather conditions influence atmospheric irradiance, solar irradiance, and radiative cooler thermal radiation in the energy balance equation, so environmental parameters must be measured in close proximity to in-field measurements.

According to the Guide to Instruments and Methods of Observation [WMO24]), the measurement of meteorological parameters shall follow standardized procedures in order to ensure data accuracy, comparability, and representativeness

Air temperature

Temperature measurements including air temperature and surface temperature of the PRC material are crucial as they are directly related to the cooling performance characterization. According to the Guide, air temperature shall be measured at a height of 1.25 m to 2.0 m above natural grass-covered ground, using a naturally or artificially ventilated screen that shields the sensor from direct and reflected solar radiation as well as precipitation. For PRC applications, it is essential to measure the ambient temperature in the immediate vicinity of the sample. Therefore, if the experiment is conducted on a concrete rooftop, it is good practice to record the ambient temperature specific to that location taking in consideration the recommendation about the height and structure of the installation. The installation site shall be sufficiently distant from artificial surfaces, with a minimum clearance equal to twice the height of nearby obstacles, and instruments shall be calibrated regularly against certified reference thermometers (Part I, Chap. 2.1.3.1–2.1.3.2; Chap. 1.3.2; Chap. 1.4.2; Annex 1.B). The screen used to shield the sensor from direct sunlight should be of high quality; otherwise, ambient temperature measurements may be affected by overheating during the day.

Sky temperature / infrared atmospheric irradiance

The performance of PRC applications strongly depends on the openness of the sky transparency window, which governs access to the cold potential in the radiative energy balance. This potential continuously varies

with atmospheric conditions such as pollution, cloud cover, and humidity. Therefore, accurate characterization of the sky transparency window is essential. To this end, two complementary instruments can be employed:

- A pyrgeometer that can provide the infrared component (for wavelength longer than 4.5 μm up to 40 μm) in terms of specific power acquired from surrounding or transmitted to the deep sky. The instrument is based on a thermopile sensor and normally its output reading is in terms of voltage. Its sensitivity is expressed in $\mu\text{V}/(\text{W}/\text{m}^2)$ and thanks to a calibration factor, specific for each device, its output can be easily converted/expressed in W/m^2 . The polarity of the output signal gives the direction of the heat exchanged via radiation (i.e. positive for incoming radiation, negative for outgoing radiation).
- An infrared thermometer with a working wavelength band located in the range between 7 μm and 13 μm able to directly indicate the “apparent” sky temperature. In this case the measured temperature value can be assimilated to that of a black body (at the corresponding absolute temperature) towards which the PRC material exchanges heat by radiation following the Stefan-Boltzmann law.

The main differences between the two instruments are:

- (a) The working wavelength band, for both in the FIR, but with different extension: above 4.5 μm for the pyrgeometer and between 7 μm and 13 μm (that is, in correspondence with the so called “sky transparency window”) in the case of radiation thermometer.
- (b) The different solid angles under which they perform measurements: close to the hemisphere for the pyrgeometer, and dependent on the ratio between working distance and minimum spot size for the radiation thermometer.

Indeed, with the appropriate choice of this instrument feature, it is possible to observe different portions of the sky at the zenith. Ideally, the best choice would be to match the solid viewing angle of the measuring instrument with that observed by the PRC material positioned in the test bed.

It is important to note that, on windy and clear sky days, the apparent sky temperature can drop below - 50 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Therefore, the minimum value of the radiation thermometer’s measuring range should be chosen as low as possible. However, only a very few commercial instruments with these features are available on the market. A possible solution to this problem suggests the implementation of a dedicated non-contact IR temperature-measuring device based on the MLX90614 Melexis thermopile that can reach minimum reading temperature as low as - 70 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ with different viewing angle options.

These two sensors are complementary in nature. The pyrgeometer provides an integrated measurement over a broad spectral range, offering an overall assessment of the infrared radiative potential. In contrast, the infrared thermometer operates over a narrower wavelength range, making it more sensitive to local spectral variations. The infrared thermometer is particularly useful for detecting clouds, which act as infrared reflectors, while the pyrgeometer helps capture the total infrared radiative flux. However, the pyrgeometer’s readings should be interpreted with caution, as they represent a scalar value obtained from integration across the entire infrared spectrum.

Relative humidity / water condensation

Humidity is one of the critical parameters that affects the sky transparency window due to the strong infrared absorption of water vapour in the atmosphere. Air humidity shall be observed at the same height as temperature, typically using ventilated psychrometers or electronic hygrometers placed within the same protective screen. The calibration of humidity sensors shall be carried out periodically, either through saturated salt solutions or in climatic chambers (Chap. 2.2.2–2.2.3.2; Chap. 2.2.5; Annex 2.A).

Solar irradiance / shadowing from obstacles

Global solar radiation shall be measured with a pyranometer compliant with ISO 9060 and WMO standards, installed horizontally and unobstructed by shading (trees, buildings, etc.), including seasonal variations. The instrument shall be mounted typically 1.5 m to 2 m above the ground or alternatively on rooftops free of reflective surfaces. Proper levelling using an integrated bubble level, frequent cleaning of the protective dome,

and periodic calibration—at least every two years against a traceable reference standard—shall be undertaken to ensure the reliability of the observations (Chap. 7.2.1 -- 7.3.2; Chap. 7.4.1; Chap. 7.5).

Wind / convective heat exchanges

Wind measurements, encompassing both speed and direction, shall be taken at the standard height of 10 m above the ground on level terrain free of obstacles within a distance at least ten times their height. In the case of rooftop installations, sensors shall be placed at least 10 m above the roof surface and no less than 1.5 times the building height. Both cup and sonic anemometers are acceptable, provided that periodic verification of instrument friction and responsiveness shall be performed (Chap. 5.1.1–5.1.2.3; Chap. 5.2; Chap. 5.4; Chap. 1.3.2).

6 Best practices for the on-site performance assessment

Based on the experiences gained during the project, in order to derive affordable measurements of cooling power and/or temperature drop, the following recommendations should be considered:

Air temperature

Measuring ambient temperature without a properly shielded weather station may cause noticeable temperature differences. Comparing temperature measurements from standalone temperature sensors (especially when exposed to direct sunlight or placed in a sealed enclosure) can result in a large temperature difference compared to those obtained using weather stations. Moreover, in case of direct cooling power measurement, an overestimation of the air temperature will lead to an incorrect and higher cooling performance of the PRC material under test. A large temperature drop will be consequently measured.

Humidity

In case the air temperature is below the dew point, a condensation occurs on the PRC and the cooling result observed is due to the subsequent evaporation process.

Solar irradiance / shadowing check

The orientation of the setup with respect to solar radiation is a critical factor. Shadows cast on the sample, whether from surrounding structures or from elements of the experimental setup itself such as the Stevenson shield must be avoided. When testing multiple materials in different sample holders, it is essential to prevent mutual shadowing or, at the very least, to ensure that all sample holders experience identical boundary conditions (e.g., equal irradiance) to avoid introducing bias into the reported.

Furthermore, whenever possible, obstacles near the experimental setup, such as buildings or trees, should be avoided, as they can obstruct the sample's access to the sky transparency window, and the tilting angle between the emitter and the sky orientation should be mentioned.

In the case of small size setups or when the dimensions allow it, a “sun shadowing check” can be applied to verify that a real net cooling effect exists. The check consists in blocking the direct sky irradiance onto the sample (i.e. by interposing a disc that screens the sun by creating a shadow on the sample) leaving, at the same time, the rest of the hemispherical solid angle unobstructed so that the sample can irradiate its thermal energy toward the sky in the IR region. In such conditions an abrupt change in both cooling power and/or temperature drop should be clearly observed.

A similar check should be repeated by instead blocking the whole upward hemisphere seen by the sample with a large obstacle blocking both solar irradiation and sky access. In this case, any cooling effect should vanish, bringing the sample temperature close to ambient temperature.

Conductive / convective heat exchanges

This type of contributions, that may positively or negatively influence the cooling power, can be kept as low as possible by maintaining the temperature of the PRC sample as close as possible to the air temperature. However, the placement of a thick foam insulation along the sides and underneath the measuring equipment

to prevent the PRC material from a direct heat exchange by conduction to the surrounding environment may be adopted. A wide range of types and products of thermal insulation materials are available on the market. The choice of the product depends on the application as well as the boundary conditions such as location, latitude, and altitude. The choice of material properties should also be suitable and relevant to the type of application. Details of the sample holder design, including material selection and dimensions, should be reported in the experiment to facilitate meaningful comparisons across different measurements.

Wind shielding

As for the convective effect, it could be useful to put, a few millimetres above the PRC sample, a thin polyethylene (PE) film. This transparent cover reduces convection heat loss and lowers the radiative cooling temperature (i.e., temperature drop). Such wind cover must have enough mechanical strength and be transparent to infrared thermal radiation in the atmospheric window. Ideally, it should represent a mechanical barrier to direct wind (forced convection), while not sealing the sample inside, to avoid the formation of a greenhouse effect overheating the air pocket surrounding the sample.

Calibration of measuring instruments

The sensors used in the experimental setup should be calibrated by accredited labs to guarantee a direct traceability towards national standards. The calibration gives assurance of accuracy and reliability of the measurement results. If calibration is not feasible, the associated measurement uncertainties should be estimated and incorporated into subsequent calculations.

Measurement uncertainty

A target uncertainty should be defined during the experimental design stage. During 21GRD03 PaRaMetriC, a target uncertainty of 10% was established for both FoMs. This must include not only instrument uncertainty but also the possible contribution of influencing parameters such as conduction and convection heat exchanges. Based on the experience gained during the project, a combined uncertainty of 10 % seems close to the lowest possible uncertainty that is reasonably reachable with state-of-the-art equipment, which should be taken into account when reporting experimental measurement data.

Without a stated final measurement uncertainty value, it is not possible to compare results from different experimental setups.

Both FoMs require the measurement of temperature differences that can be very small. To this purpose, it is advisable to directly use a differential thermocouple rather than two individual temperature sensors. Moreover, a multi-junction differential thermocouple can be considered to increase the measurement resolution.

Night-time cooling performance

It is important to analyse the trend of the PRC material during both daytime and night-time hours; night-time measurements can be used to isolate the contribution of the infrared emissivity, since the nighttime response of the PRC ceases to depend on the very critical solar reflectance parameter.

Heat-exchange medium

The PRC sample can be coupled with different kinds of materials/media and substrates (air, water, metallic materials). In all cases, a good thermal contact between the temperature sensor and the medium should be assured. It is crucial to maintain a uniform temperature in the medium. This can be achieved by avoiding still air or air bubbles in the liquid, as well as by keeping the minimum thermal capacity, or using minimal amounts of highly conductive thermal paste to ensure thermal contact. The temperature measurement protocol, specifically, how the sensor is attached to the substrate, should be clearly reported to enable meaningful comparisons with other experiments.

Transient response VS thermal inertia of exchange medium

Considering the possible rapid change over the time of the environmental conditions and especially those related to solar irradiance, in order to observe such fast transients, the thermal inertia of the medium

underneath the PRC material (air, liquid or metal substrates) has to be considered and kept as small as possible.

Absolute or relative measurements

A relative measurement could be useful only to compare different PRC materials with respect to the same reference material. Such reference materials should be well-characterised beforehand, possibly with publicly available characterisation data, or easily procured by different research groups. The reference material should ideally be known for exhibiting a net radiative cooling power, in order to determine whether the material under test exhibits a higher or lower cooling performance compared to the reference one. In order to characterise the PRC material in terms of its actual cooling power and/or temperature drop, an absolute measurement is needed.

Measurement duration

Whenever possible, measurement should be planned with a duration of at least 24h to capture both the daytime and nighttime behaviour of the PRC material under test. Cloudy and overcast conditions are also interesting to study, as they should exhibit a clear obliteration of the cooling power associated to the coating. Having several days with comparable sky conditions is also useful to perform a statistical analysis of temperature drop and/or cooling power values during fixed time windows.

Synchronous FoM measurements

Whenever possible, the two main figures of merit should be ideally measured simultaneously on two nominally identical samples exposed to the same ambient conditions. This can guarantee their subsequent comparability and help identify correlations between the two trends with respect to rapid changes in ambient conditions.

7 References

- [Ail21] Aili, Ablimit, Xiaobo Yin, and Ronggui Yang. "Global radiative sky cooling potential adjusted for population density and cooling demand." *Atmosphere* 12.11 (2021): 1379.
- [Ber03] Berger, Xavier, and Joseph Bathiebo. "Directional spectral emissivities of clear skies." *Renewable Energy* 28.12 (2003): 1925-1933.
- [Bij24] Bijarniya, Jay Prakash, Jahar Sarkar, and Pralay Maiti. "Experimental performance characteristics of the daytime radiative cooler at various surface orientations." *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells* 272 (2024): 112906.
- [Bu23] Bu, Kunlang, et al. "Consistent assessment of the cooling performance of radiative cooling materials." *Advanced Functional Materials* 33.51 (2023): 2307191.
- [Che16] Chen, Zhen, et al. "Radiative cooling to deep sub-freezing temperatures through a 24-h day-night cycle." *Nature communications* 7.1 (2016): 13729.
- [Fan23] Fan, Fan, et al. "A simple, accurate, and universal method for characterizing and comparing radiative cooling materials and devices." *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer* 200 (2023): 123494.
- [Gol17] Goldstein, Eli A., Aaswath P. Raman, and Shanhui Fan. "Sub-ambient non-evaporative fluid cooling with the sky." *Nature Energy* 2.9 (2017): 1-7.
- [Gra81] Granqvist, C. G., and A. Hjortsberg. "Radiative cooling to low temperatures: General considerations and application to selectively emitting SiO films." *Journal of Applied Physics* 52.6 (1981): 4205-4220.
- [Had25] Haddouche, M. Reda, et al. "Experimental investigation of parameters influencing Test Box and material behavior in daytime Radiative Cooling measurements." *Heat Transfer* (2025).
- [JCGM08] Joint Committee for Guides in Metrology "Evaluation of measurement data—Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement." *Int. Organ. Stand. Geneva ISBN* 50 (2008): 134.
- [Ler19] Leroy, A., et al. "High-performance subambient radiative cooling enabled by optically selective and thermally insulating polyethylene aerogel." *Science advances* 5.10 (2019): eaat9480.
- [Ler22] Leroy, A., et al. "Thermal transport in solar-reflecting and infrared-transparent polyethylene aerogels." *International Journal of Heat and Mass Transfer* 184 (2022): 122307.
- [Lio24a] Lio, Giuseppe Emanuele, et al. "Radiative cooling potential of a water-based paint formulation under realistic application conditions." *ACS Applied Optical Materials* 2.12 (2024): 2459-2468.
- [Lio24b] Lio, Giuseppe Emanuele, et al. "Nanoporous film layers to enhance the performance of passive radiative cooling paint mixtures." *International Journal of Thermophysics* 45.11 (2024): 153.
- [Man18] Mandal, Jyotirmoy, et al. "Hierarchically porous polymer coatings for highly efficient passive daytime radiative cooling." *Science* 362.6412 (2018): 315-319.
- [Ram14] Raman, Aaswath P., et al. "Passive radiative cooling below ambient air temperature under direct sunlight." *Nature* 515.7528 (2014): 540-544.
- [Sui24] Sui, Chenxi, and Po-Chun Hsu. "Standardizing the thermodynamic definition of daytime subambient radiative cooling." *ACS Energy Letters* 9.6 (2024): 2997-3000.
- [Tak19] Takahashi, Eisuke, and Osamu Kaneko. "A new approach to prediction of responses in closed loop systems based on the direct usage of one-shot experimental data." *Transactions of the Society of Instrument and Control Engineers* 55.4 (2019): 324-330.
- [Tia23] Tian, Dongdong, Jianshun Zhang, and Zhi Gao. "The advancement of research in cool roof: Super cool roof, temperature-adaptive roof and crucial issues of application in cities." *Energy and Buildings* 291 (2023): 113131.
- [Tic23] Tichý, D., et al. Report on the collection and production of candidate passive radiative cooling materials, and identification of figures of merit to evaluate their cooling performance. Zenodo (2023) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10260070>

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- [Wan21] Wang, Tong, et al. "A structural polymer for highly efficient all-day passive radiative cooling." *Nature communications* 12.1 (2021): 365.
- [Wer25] Werle, Jeremy, et al. "Open-hardware platform for synchronous performance testing of multiple passive radiative cooling materials." *Cell Reports Physical Science* 6.7 (2025).
- [WMO24] World Meteorological Organization (WMO) "Guide to Instruments and Methods of Observation Volume I –Measurement of Meteorological Variables" WMO-No. 8 (2024)
- [Won23] Wong, Ross YM, et al. "Critical sky temperatures for passive radiative cooling." *Renewable Energy* 211 (2023): 214-226.
- [Zha19a] Zhao, Bin, et al. "General strategy of passive sub-ambient daytime radiative cooling." *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells* 199 (2019): 108-113.
- [Zha19b] Zhao, Dongliang, et al. "Radiative sky cooling: Fundamental principles, materials, and applications." *Applied Physics Reviews* 6.2 (2019).
- [Zho23] Zhou, Lyu, Xiaobo Yin, and Qiaoqiang Gan. "Best practices for radiative cooling." *Nature Sustainability* 6.9 (2023): 1030-1032.